

PROBLEM-SOLVING INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PHYSICS STUDENTS IN ORUK ANAM LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study investigated problem-solving instructional strategies on the academic performance of Physics students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses guided the study. A quasi-experimental design employing a pretest-posttest control group was adopted. The sample comprised 106 Senior Secondary II Physics students drawn from two public secondary schools in the study area, randomly assigned to experimental and control groups. The research instrument, Physics Performance Test, was pilot-tested and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.76. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to address the research questions while inferential statistics of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that the problem-solving instructional strategy significantly enhanced student's academic performance in Physics compared to the discussion method. Additionally, a significant difference was observed in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught using the problem-solving strategy. Based on these findings, it is recommended that Physics teachers adopt problem-solving instructional strategies to promote deeper understanding, boost learners' confidence, and improve overall academic performance in Physics.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Discussion Method, Gender, Problem-solving Strategy, Physics.

Introduction

Education serves as a fundamental pillar of societal development, fostering citizens who are knowledgeable, skilled and self-reliant. It equips individuals with the essential competencies and capacities required to participate meaningfully and contribute productively to the advancement of their communities. Education according to Mark (2021), can be defined as the sensible, hopeful and respectful cultivation of learning carried out in the belief that ought to have the chance to share in life. Education enhances the quality of life, and the method to acquire wealth of knowledge is via education. Developing countries see education as the key which will unlock their national resources, the study growth and presence and the most effective antidote to their problems and lack of knowledge. Physics is a branch of science that explores the underlying causes of natural events and the laws and principles that governs them. It enables individuals to comprehend their surroundings and assess uncertainties, leading to inventions and the development of new technologies. With advancements in technology, the need for physics in

everyday and professional contexts has steadily increased. As a result, physics education has gained significant importance. In our knowledge-driven era, a key goal of modern science and physics education is to nurture individuals who can research, analyze, and connect scientific concepts to their daily experiences, apply scientific methods to solve problems, and adopt a scientific perspective on life.

According to Nnaji (2021), in Esenowo (2025), Physics is one of the science subjects at the secondary school level that deals with the study of laws that determine the structure of the universe with reference to matter and energy in the universe. Effective physics teaching requires student-centered approaches that actively engage students in the learning process. As Cildir (2012) notes, physics involves applying concepts to real-world situations, making problem-solving strategy a particularly suitable method for teaching this subject. By using such approaches, students can develop a deeper understanding of Physics principles and their applications.

Despite physics being a crucial component of science and technology, Nigerian secondary schools struggle with low student enrollment and poor performance in the subject (Osei et al., 2015). Nnaji (2021) observed that there is a serious disconnection between the ways of learning and the methods of teaching in physics, and most teachers use the conventional methods they were taught with for today's teaching, thereby resulting in half-baked knowledge impartation to students in physics.

Problem-solving is an effective teaching strategy that promotes deep learning of basic facts, concepts, and procedures, while also fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills within real-world contexts. This approach encourages students to explore and investigate problems, and in Physics education, it's characterized by collaborative interaction between students and teachers. Teachers provide just enough guidance to set the stage for problem-solving, while students work to clarify, interpret, and develop solutions. By accepting all answers in a non-judgmental way, teachers create a safe space for students to think creatively and take ownership of their learning. Through insightful questioning and coaching, teachers guide students without spoon-feeding them, allowing them to develop problem-solving skills and build new knowledge through reflective thinking. This strategy is particularly valuable in physics education as it engages students, boosts motivation, and enhances learning outcomes.

Problem-solving strategy is to know what to-do in the situation of not knowing what to -do. Problem-solving strategy is not only finding the correct answer but also is an action that covers a wide mental period and abilities (Bunkure et al., 2018). Problem solving involves application of thinking and reasoning to various kinds of problems encountered in life (Abasi & Ado, 2021). It is an integral part of developmental activities and provides opportunities for children to practice what they have learned by applying their learning situations. The amount of practice needed by any learner is reduced if he understands the concepts and skills to be practiced.

According to Ergun (2010), problems can be categorized into two types: routine and non-routine. Routine problems, often found in physics textbooks, involve basic arithmetic operations and word problems that aim to develop students' operational skills and apply mathematical equations to real-life situations. In contrast, non-routine problems require more complex thinking, involving data organization, classification, and relationship-building. Problem-solving strategies can be applied to both types of problems. Cooperative learning methods, such as collaborative learning and academic debate, can be effective in building ideas and promoting problem-

solving skills.

Using problem-solving strategies can be more beneficial than traditional methods as it fosters leadership, sharing, critical thinking, and individualized instruction, ultimately leading to more effective learning outcomes. In the Problem-solving strategy, the role of the teacher is to describe to the students the terminal performance that constitutes the solution to the problem. Assess the students' entering behavior for the concept and principles they will need to solve the problem. As a teaching strategy, problem-solving entails training the students on how to solve problems by proceeding in a logical step-by-step manner from a problem state to its solution.

In the course of concentrating on the Physics students', gender usually suffice. Adewumi (2024) defined gender as the classification of human beings on the basis of sex due to the roles they perform. Gender has also remained an important issue that is relevant to the field of education because it has been linked with students' performance. According to Awodun (2015), gender differences have become critical issues of concern around the world, most especially to educators and researchers.

Gender refers to the classification of individuals as male or female, and gender differences have long been a critical issue in education due to their association with variations in academic performance. Disparities in performance between male and female students have been linked to unequal access to learning experiences essential for mastering subjects such as Physics. This inequality is often shaped by traditional cultural norms and attitude that restrict female participation in certain educational and experiential activities.

The teaching and learning of physics demand a considerable level of cognitive engagement. However, students differ in cognitive strength, which is often influenced by gender, leading to observable disparities in academic performance between male and female learners. Gender stereotypes significantly contributed to these differences, shaped by factors such as Instructional methodologies parental support, and advocacy initiatives promoting female empowerment and academic advancement, particularly at the tertiary level. Conversely, involvement in extracurricular activities, socio-economic pressures, gendered ideologies, and financial constraints frequently affect male students' academic performance. Addressing these challenges through continuous education, sensitization on gender stereotype, and the implementation of inclusive policy measures is essential for sustaining both genders in the educational system and fostering national development. Consequently, this study considers gender as a moderating variable, recognizing its potential influence on student's academic performance when exposed to a problem-solving instructional strategy.

Empirically, Bunkure (2018) findings revealed that the problem-solving strategy had a significant effect on students' academic performance in Physics problem solving than conventional teaching method. There was also a significant difference in performance between male and female students in problem solving. Results show that the treatment groups were highly motivated. It was therefore recommended that the problem-solving strategy should be adopted in teaching Physics to enhance students' academic performance. According to Lorenzo (2015), students using problem-solving methods were more confident and had a higher ability to solve difficult problems. Udo and Ursula (2024) revealed that a significant difference existed among the mean scores of students in physics taught using problem-solving method and lecture method in favour of group taught using problem-solving instructional strategy. The study of Obochi (2021) and Okafor et al. (2023) shows that the problem-solving

strategy enhanced students' academic performance in biology compared to traditional methods of teaching. Adewumi (2023) showed that there is a significant difference between the academic performances mean score of the students exposed to concepts using problem-solving strategy in biology compared with their counterparts taught using the traditional methods.

Nzewi (2017) indicates that females prefer teaching strategies that encourages students' participation in designing experiments, making inference, proposing and testing hypotheses. Therefore, while understating the need to address gender differences represents a vital step, making education gender responsive will require a genuine commitment to provide teaching-learning experiences that reflect male and female differences. Adewumi (2024) revealed in his study that there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students using problem-solving strategy in biology and compared with their counterparts taught using lecture strategy. Okafor (2021) and Ekon and Eni (2015) showed that women were not only under-represented but their level in the field of science and technology were low compared to their male counterparts. Despite the extensive research on instructional approaches for teaching Physics in senior secondary schools, limited attention has been given to the application of problem-solving strategies in Physics education particularly within Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Addressing this gap is crucial; as the quality of teacher preparation and instructional methods significantly influences students' enrollment, engagement, and academic outcomes. Moreover, existing studies on gender differences in academic performance have produced mixed findings—some reporting no significant difference between male and female students while others highlight disparities favouring one gender over the other. These inconsistencies underscore the need for further empirical investigation into the effect of problem-solving instructional strategies on student's academic performance in Physics.

Statement of the problem

The persistent issue of poor and inconsistent academic performance among Physics students remains a major concern for educators and stakeholders in Akwa Ibom State. Recent trends in the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) results, as reported by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO) chief examiner's between 2020 and 2024, indicate a steady decline in students' performance in Physics. One possible contributing factor is the continued reliance of many secondary school teachers on traditional discussion methods, which limit students' opportunities to explore, observe, and interact with their physical environment. This lack of experiential engagement restricts the development of critical and creative thinking skills necessary for meaningful learning in Physics. Consequently the persistent underperformance of students may be attributed to the use of ineffective instructional strategies. In response to this challenge, the present study investigates the effect of problem-solving instructional strategy on the academic performance of Physics students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate problem-solving strategy and academic performance of Physics students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the difference in the mean performance scores of students taught Physics using a problem-solving

strategy and those taught using discussion method.

2. Determine the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Physics using a problem-solving strategy.

Research Questions

To guide the study two null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the mean performance scores of students taught Physics using a problem-solving strategy and those taught with discussion method?

2. What are the mean performance scores of male and female students when taught Physics using problem-solving strategy?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught Physics using a problem-solving strategy and their counterparts taught using discussion method.

2. There is no significant between the mean performance scores of male and female students when exposed to problem-solving strategy and their counterparts taught using the discussion method.

Methods

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design of the pretest-posttest control group. Two groups—experimental and control were selected from the population of Senior Secondary School Two (SS II) students in the Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The experimental group received instruction through the problem-solving strategy, while the control group was taught using the discussion method. The study population comprised 476 SS II students enrolled in public secondary schools within the study area. A sample of 106 students, consisting of 48 males and 58 females, was selected using a simple random sampling technique. Two public secondary schools were randomly chosen, and one intact class from each school was assigned to either the experimental or control group. The research instrument used was the Physics Performance Test (PPT), developed by the researcher. The instrument's validity was established. Conversely, involvement in extracurricular activities, socio-economic pressures, gendered ideologies, and financial constraints frequently affect male students' academic performance by one experienced secondary school Physics teacher, who is also a WAEC/NECO examiner, and two lecturers from the University of Uyo, one from the Department of Curriculum and Instructional Technology and the other from the Department of Test and Measurement. The lesson notes and marking schemes for both groups were also reviewed for face validity and appropriateness. The PPT was pilot-tested to determine reliability, yielding a coefficient of 0.78. The instruments were administered to both the experimental and control groups before and after the treatment which lasted for 4-weeks. Data obtained were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One: What are the mean performance scores of student's thought Physics, using problem-solving strategy, and those thought with discussion method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation performance scores of Physics students exposed to Problem strategy and those exposed to discussion Method

Teaching methods	n	Pretest Mean	Pretest SD	Post test Mean	Post test SD	Mean Gain
Problem Solving	54	42.89	9.10	52.92	8.70	10.03
Discussion Method	52	45.13	9.11	51.66	9.66	6.53
Mean diff				1.26		3.50

Table 1 shows that, the mean score of the pretest in problem-solving group was 42.89 with associated standard deviation score of 9.10, while the mean score of the post test was 52.92 with standard deviation of 8.70 and mean gain of 10.03 was obtained. In the Discussion method group, the pretest had mean score of 45.13 with standard deviation of 9.11, whereas the posttest had mean score of 51.66 with standard deviation of 9.66 and mean gain of 6.53 obtained. The mean difference of 3.50 was obtained in favour of the problem-solving group.

Research Question Two: What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Physics using a problem-solving Strategy?

Table 2 Mean performance scores of male and female students exposed to the Problem-solving strategy in Physics

Method	Gender	n	Pretest Mean	Pre test SD	Post test Mean	Post test SD	Gain Mean
Problem solving	Male	29	43.15	9.16	54.16	10.35	11.01
	Female	25	42.58	9.22	51.58	8.99	9.00
Mean diff			0.57		2.58		2.01

Table 2 shows that the mean score of the males in the pretest group was 43.15 with standard deviation of 9.16 while in the posttest group they had a mean score of 54.16 with associated standard deviation of 10.35 and mean gain of 11.01 was obtained. In the pretest group the females had a mean score of 42.58 with Standard deviation of 9.22 whereas in the posttest group they had a mean Score of 51.58 with Standard deviation of 8.99 and mean gain of 9.00 was obtained. The mean difference of 2.01 was obtained in favour of the males.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught Physics using the problem-solving strategy and those taught with discussion method.

Table 3 Analysis of coverence (ANCOVA) of students' academic performance mean scores in Physics of those exposed to Problem-solving strategy and those exposed to discussion method.

Source	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Correcte Model					
Intercept	476.91	1	476.91	403.82	.0021
Pretest	7422.93	1	7422.93	7.06	.0091
Method (Group)	129.74	1	129.74		.0000
Error	1893.33	103	18.38		
Total	9922.90	105			
Corrected Total	9446.00	105			

*Significant at $P>0.05$ level of significance

Table 4.5 was used to determine whether students taught Physics with problem solving strategy had significant difference in their mean performance scores from that of those exposed to discussion method. It shows that the teaching method (group) has a statistically significant effect on the students post test performance ($F = 7.06$, $p = 0.0091$), after controlling for pre-test scores. Hence, the null hypothesis one, was rejected and inference drawn that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of students exposed to problem-solving strategy in Physics and that of those exposed to discussion method. This confirms that the Problem-solving strategy is more effective than the discussion method for improving physics performance.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of the male and female students exposed to Problem-solving strategy.

Table 4 Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of male and female mean performance scors difference that one exposed to problem solving strategy in Biology

Source	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model					
Intercept	549.999	1	549.999	29.93	.0001
PRETEST	3035.345	1	3035.345	165.18	.0000
GENDER	149.974	1	149.974	8.16	.0062
Error	937.184	51	18.38		
Total	4672.50	53			
Corrected Total	4122.50	53			

*Significant at $P>0.05$ level of significance

Table 4 was used to determine whether there is significant difference in the mean performance scores of male

and female students taught physics with problem-solving strategy. Table 4 shows that the gender effect is statistically significant ($F = 8.16, p = 0.0062$) indicating a significant difference in post-test performance between male and female students after controlling for pre-test scores. Hence, the null hypothesis two was rejected, and inference drawn that there is significant difference exists between the mean scores of the male and female students exposed to problem-solving strategy in Physics. Male perform significantly better than female under the problem-solving strategy.

Discussion of Findings

The result from Table 1 shows that the performance of students in physics was better when taught with problem-solving strategy. Also, hypothesis 1 in Table 3 shows a significant difference between the mean performance scores of students exposed to the Problem-solving problem strategy in Physics than those exposed to discussion method. The students taught physics using problem-solving methods performed better than those taught with discussion method. This outcome is anticipated as the problem-solving strategy utilizes a systematic approach that guides students through the processes of identifying problems, analyzing underlying factors, generating alternative solutions, evaluating these options, and implementing the most effective course of action. The strategy fosters active learning by promoting meaningful engagement with the subject matter through experiential and participatory activities.

The above findings agree with Oyawole (2012) whose study revealed that there was a significant mean difference between students taught using problem-solving strategy and those taught using lecture method. Similarly, the present findings agree with Tsoho (2011) who found a significant difference between the mean scores of students in biology when taught using problem-solving and lecture methods in favour of problem solving in teaching biology and other sciences. The finding also supports Okafor et al. (2023), Adewumi (2023) and Obochi (2021), whose findings revealed that the problem-solving strategy enhanced the students' academic performance compared to traditional teaching methods.

The findings from Table 2 show mean performance scores of male and female students exposed to problem-solving strategy in Physics, with a difference of 2.01 obtained in favour of male students. The result of hypothesis 2 also showed that there is significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female students exposed to problem-solving strategy in Physics.

This result is in contrast with the finding of Adewumi (2024), who revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to genetic concepts using problem-solving strategy in biology and compared with their counterparts taught using lecture strategy. The findings of this study opposed the finding of Ajibade (2019), in his study on sex differences and students' academic performance in Secondary Schools found that female students perform better than their male counterparts while Iwendi (2012) found male students outperform their female counterparts.

Female students often respond more positively to instructional approaches that involve active participation, such as designing experiments, drawing conclusions, and formulating and testing hypotheses—practices that are particularly relevant in physics education. Therefore, while acknowledging gender differences is an important initial step, attending truly gender-responsive requires a deliberate commitment to developing teaching and

learning experiences that effectively address and accommodate the distinct learning needs of both male and female students.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the problem-solving instructional strategy significantly improves students' academic performance in Physics, surpassing the outcomes achieved through the discussion method. The study also revealed that gender exerts a significant influence on student's performance when exposed to the problem-solving strategy. This implies that both male and female students achieve high levels of academic success in Physics when taught using problem-solving strategy.

Recommendations

It is therefore recommended that:

1. Biology teachers should consistently implement problem-solving instructional strategies in their teaching. This approach will empower students to take greater responsibility for their own learning within the classroom, thereby enhancing their academic performance.
2. Non-governmental organization (NGOs), ministries of education, and relevant government agencies should organize regular training sessions, workshops, and seminars to equip teachers with the necessary skills for effectively applying problem-solving strategies in the teaching of science subjects.

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